

TASK SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS APPLICATION FOR ONLINE CLASS SCHEDULE OPTIMIZATION

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University lesson timetabling is a complex problem involving assigning times and locations to various courses while meeting complicated constraints and factors. Effective lesson dispatching could include several processing steps and a set of input parameters and constraints. [1] The generic classification of fundamental algorithms and techniques commonly used for this task are divided into several groups. Graph coloring algorithms are essential in solving the timetabling problem, where each course can be considered a node in a graph, and edges represent conflicts (i.e., courses that cannot be scheduled simultaneously). The goal is to color the graph (assign times) so that no two adjacent nodes (conflicting courses) share the same color (time slot). [2] Constraint-based methods involve formulating the timetabling problem as a constraint satisfaction problem (CSP), where constraints like instructor availability, room capacity, and time slots must all be considered. Solvers then find solutions that satisfy all the constraints. Genetic algorithms (GA) are used for more complex timetabling problems. [3] GAs simulate natural evolutionary processes to generate solutions using operators like mutation, crossover, and selection. They are beneficial for exploring an ample solution space and finding near-optimal solutions when exact solutions are computationally infeasible. [4] Simulated annealing is a pattern inspired by the process of annealing in metallurgy. It's a probabilistic technique that explores the solution space by occasionally allowing worse solutions, which helps avoid local minima and potentially find a global optimum in the scheduling solution space. Tabu search is an iterative search technique where each move (or solution alteration) is evaluated, and the best move is made, even if it worsens the solution. The algorithm keeps a list of "tabu" (forbidden) moves to avoid cycling back to previously explored solutions. [5] Integer linear programming (ILP) models the timetabling problem as a set of linear equations with integer solutions. It's highly accurate and can perfectly optimize to the set constraints but can be computationally intensive for large datasets that are standard in university settings. Heuristic and meta-heuristic techniques include a variety of strategies designed to solve the problem efficiently by approximating the best solution, especially when the search space is vast or complex. Common heuristics include ant colony optimization, particle swarm optimization, and greedy algorithms. Hybrid methods are a combination of these methods that exploit the strengths of multiple approaches. For

example, a hybrid of genetic algorithms and simulated annealing can yield better results by combining the explorative properties of both methods. [6]

These algorithms are employed in different combinations and tailored to the specific needs and constraints of the educational institution. Effective timetabling directly impacts academic effectiveness and resource utilization, making these algorithms critical in educational administration software. [7]

The set of criteria being investigated for the lesson dispatching optimization task is defined below:

1. Set of the lesson dispatching criteria (dedicated to online educational form)
 - 1.1. Basic criteria (applicable both for offline and online educational forms)
 - 1.1.1. Curriculum sizing (the number of hours allocated for the discipline in the curriculum)
 - 1.1.2. Lecturer's time slots (the available predefined time slots of the particular lecturer)
 - 1.2. Investigated criteria (additional criteria applicable to online educational form only)
 - 1.2.1. Discipline weight factor (the weight of discipline importance for a particular specialty)
 - 1.2.2. Time slot priorities (the time slot priority based on the group course)
 - 1.2.3. Knowledge control form (is the knowledge control form synchronous or asynchronous)
 - 1.2.4. Lesson sequencing (scheduling lectures and practical lessons of the same discipline in a sequence)
 - 1.2.5. Load balancing (the balanced distribution of the lessons on the weekdays)
 - 1.2.6. Output evaluation (the final step of the generated lesson distribution verification)

For the proper resolution of this task, the complex approach is the most effective, involving and combining several standard algorithms and techniques for the particular criteria from the set of defined ones:

1. Constraint-based methods: This technique is compelling for handling rigid and soft constraints. It is effectively used to ensure all essential criteria, such as curriculum sizing and lecturer's time slots, are met while also incorporating investigated criteria like discipline weight factor, time slot priorities, and the form of knowledge control. Constraint programming can adaptively enforce rules and preferences defined in the set of dispatching criteria.

2. Integer linear programming (ILP): Given its ability to optimally solve problems with multiple objectives and constraints, ILP is particularly efficient for the defined set of criteria. It can describe the problem with mathematical precision, effectively handling complex constraints like lesson sequencing and load balancing. ILP can also be configured to prioritize certain constraints over others, such as giving higher priority to the discipline weight factor or load balancing.

3. Heuristic and meta-heuristic techniques: Algorithms like genetic algorithms and simulated annealing could be beneficial when the scheduling problem has many

potential configurations and no clear optimal solution. These are particularly useful for handling the output evaluation and finding acceptable solutions in a reasonable amount of time when exact methods might be too slow due to the complexity of constraints.

4. Hybrid methods: Given the diversity and complexity of the constraints in the set of criteria defined, combining different algorithms might yield the best results. For instance, starting with a constraint-based approach to establish a feasible baseline that meets all hard constraints and then using a genetic algorithm to explore variations that optimize the soft constraints, like time slot priorities and discipline weight, could be effective.

Conclusion: In this investigation's scope, the classification of the existing vital algorithms and techniques applicable to the university lesson timetabling task has been provided. The set of the algorithm criteria has been formulated. The resulting approach to task resolution has been concluded as a combination of constraint-based methods, integer linear programming, heuristic and meta-heuristic techniques, and hybrid methods. This result allows using the most effective strategies for the particular criteria and constraints to ensure the optimized calculation with reduced algorithmic errors during the lesson dispatching process.

References

1. How technology shapes learning in higher education [Электронний ресурс] – Режим доступу до ресурсу: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/education/our-insights/how-technology-is-shaping-learning-in-higher-education> – Назва з екрана (Дата звернення: 06.04.2024).
2. Voloshinov S., Kruglyk V., Osadchyi V., Osadcha K., Symonenko S. Realities and prospects of distance learning at higher education institutions of Ukraine // *Ukr. J. Educ. Stud. Inf. Technol.* – 2020. – Vol. 8. – P. 1–16. – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.32919/uesit.2020.01.01>.
3. Galynska O., Bilous S. Remote learning during the war: challenges for higher education in Ukraine // *Int. Sci. J. Educ. Linguist.* – 2022. – № 1. – P. 1–6. – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.46299/j.isjel.20220105.01>.
4. Kosolap A.I., Dubovik T.M. Optimization of timetable at the university // *Radio Electron. Comput. Sci. Control.* – 2021. – P. 175–183. – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.15588/1607-3274-2021-3-15>.
5. Supporting distance learning with eduMEET in Ukraine [Электронний ресурс] – Режим доступу до ресурсу: <https://www.inthefieldstories.net/supporting-distance-learning-with-edumeet-in-ukraine/> – Назва з екрана (Дата звернення: 06.04.2024).
6. Çerkez Y. How to create university-wide timetables using free, open-source software [Электронний ресурс] – Режим доступу до ресурсу: <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/how-create-universitywide-timetables-using-free-opensource-software> – Назва з екрана (Дата звернення: 06.04.2024).
7. UniTime | University Timetabling [Электронний ресурс] – Режим доступу до ресурсу: <https://www.unitime.org/index.php?tab=0> – Назва з екрана (Дата звернення: 06.04.2024).